

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

DISEASE AND PEST INFECTION RATE OF NEWLY INTRODUCED PEACH VARIETIES TO AZERBAIJAN

Basti Asadova

Ph.d., Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University

Faika Aslanova

Baku State University, Azerbaijan

Zamina Sarhadova

Fruit growing and tea growing scientific research institute

Abstract

One of today's main requirements is to obtain agricultural products (including fruit) that meet the requirements of the market economy and have high quality indicators, which is always considered one of the priority directions in the agricultural field. The development of this field, along with a number of factors, depends on the resistance of the cultivated or introduced planting material against diseases and pests. Studying the resistance of fruit plants to diseases and pests, choosing economically important varieties, and organizing measures to combat them in optimal periods ensure the correct and efficient use of financial resources in the production of quality products to farmers (peasants).

Keywords: introduction, infectious diseases, disease, peach, fruit plants

Infectious diseases in fruit plants are caused by various microorganisms, chromistas, protozoa, fungi, actinomycetes, bacteria, mycoplasmas and viruses. Diseases are the result of the disruption of physiological processes occurring in various organs of the plant (root, stem, branch, leaf, pod, fruit, etc.) due to the influence of fungi, viruses, bacteria, deformation, wilting, rotting, circular and striped spots, yellowness, redness, swelling, sap flow, drying, decay, etc. It manifests itself with abnormal signs, and according to its origin, it is divided into 2 groups, non-infectious and infectious [1, 4-12].

In his research, N.N. Leonov observed a 7.6-11.0% increase in productivity in the combination of Baktophyt biofungicide with Skor and Khorus fungicides against fruit rot disease. M. Meland and others. and in his research studies on early ripening peach varieties, he states that none of these varieties have commercial value in terms of productivity and most varieties are resistant to leaf curl.[14-20, 7,8]

Taking into account the impact of diseases and pests on the productivity of plants and the quality indicators of fruits, the economic biological characteristics of 18 peach varieties of newly introduced Spanish origin were studied in Guba-Khachmaz economic region, and moniliosis (*Monilia cinirea*), hole spotting or clusterosporiosis, which are widespread diseases on these varieties, were studied. *Clasterosporium carpophilum*), powdery mildew (*Sphaerotheca pannosa*), leaf curl (*Taphrina deformans*), and pests include green peach moth (*Myzus persicae* subss. *persicae*), red fruit mite (*Tetranychus urticae*) and eastern fruit eater (*Grapholitha molesta*), etc. Harmful organisms have been detected and information about them is given below [2,3].

Moniliosis (*Monilia cinirea*) disease is a source of serious threat to the productivity of the peach plant, flowers, stems, branches and fruits of the plant are in-

fectured with this disease. The petals, pistil tube and stamen organs of infected flowers turn brown and spread throughout the flower. Diseased flowers on the branch wither and mummify. Fruit infection usually occurs during fruit ripening. The first symptom is observed by the formation of one or more brown spots on the skin of the fruit. A light brown ring forms around the spots. The rot begins to move towards the fruit pulp, but the spot does not form holes in the fruit. After 1-3 days, conidial pads appear on these spots. Over time, the mass of mycelium on the fruit completely covers the fruit and causes it to dry. Dried fruits become mummified and remain a source of infection for the plant to become infected with this disease again in the next year while hanging from the branch. Corollas infected from the side of the flower stalk turn brown, and thin corollas dry up completely. On thick branches, canker sores are formed, and the parenchyma tissue under these sores is damaged and turns brown. In rainy and humid weather, the flow of cysts around the wound is observed. Rainy and humid weather conditions in summer create favorable conditions for the development of this disease. As a measure against the disease, it is suggested to collect the infected fruits after flowering and to cut the infected branches slightly above the healthy tissue and burn them. In the years of research, the complex control measures against the diseases of cluster spot (*clasterosporiosis*), powdery mildew, and leaf curl prevented the development of moniliosis and the percentage of infection in the varieties was low.

Powdery mildew (*Sphaerotheca pannosa*) disease. In early spring, the peach plant is infected with leaves, pods and fruits, and the disease manifests itself in the form of a floury appearance of the leaves located at the tips of the newly developed pods. The color of such leaves is partially light, deformed, often twisted in the shape of a boat along the main vein. The lower side of the leaf blade becomes bare, the lower part is covered with a white, mealy coating and curls inward, and it has

a slightly convex shape on top. After a period of time, the leaves become reddish, dry and fall prematurely. The tips of the shoots become dull and prevent the formation of buds. In the case of severe infection, the stems dry up and become covered with a white-gray coating in autumn. If the disease occurs during fertilization, the fruits are dropped without development. Infected fruits do not develop well and cracks are observed in the skin. The disease affects the quantity and quality of next year's crop in the plant. Weakening of development, premature shedding of leaves, yield loss, 76 quality of fruits, decrease of plant's resistance to low temperatures are characteristic features of this disease. Based on the observations, since there are optimal conditions (+10...+25C) for the development of the causative agent in our region, as an agrotechnical control measure against powdery mildew, cleaning the inner part of the tree canopy from extra buds and cutting and neutralizing the infected branches, selecting and planting varieties resistant to the disease, in the phase of relative silence, before and immediately after flowering (when 5-10% infection is detected), chemical control with one of the systemic and contact effective fungicides is suggested.

The causative agent of leaf curl disease is *Taphrina deformans* fungus. It is one of the most widespread and dangerous diseases of the peach plant, and the leaves, stems, flowers and fruits of the plant are infected with this disease. It is found in all peach-growing regions of Azerbaijan. As a result of infection with this disease, the process of respiration and transpiration in the leaves of the plant does not go normally. Within 8-10 days from the onset of the disease, a white wax coating forms on the underside of the infected leaves. The disease spreads immediately after the formation of young leaves. The development of leaf curl disease occurs in cool, moist weather during bud opening. Most infections are observed in early spring when the first leaves are formed. Diseased leaves turn yellow and white and twist into a spiral shape. Early infected leaves do not develop, and with low infection only part of the leaf is diseased. Diseased leaves are thicker than normal leaves. The leaves change color, thicken, curl, become brittle by losing elasticity. Infected leaves turn brown after remaining on the tree for some time. Thick red bumps (small tumors) are formed on the pods and fruits. If the disease occurs during the opening of the shoots, the inter-joint distances become shorter and dry, as the stem cannot develop. Over time, these bumps turn black and split the fruit to the core. It is possible to protect the plant from this disease if it is treated with one of the appropriate drugs in the stage of relative calmness, in the stage when the shoots are swollen before flowering, in the pink cone stage and during the vegetation period (when 5-10% infection is detected in the plant) [5,6].

Hole spotting or clusterosporiosis (*Clasterosporium carpophilum*). According to our observations, the peach plant is most infected with the disease compared to other stone fruit plants (plum, cherry, cherry, cherry, etc.). It is most common in the territories of Guba-Khachmaz economic regions. The disease infects all above-ground organs of the plant (leaf, flower, shoot, fruit, fruit, branch, stem, etc.). In early spring,

diseased shoots become brightly colored as a result of sap flow and can easily break off from the branch. The disease is propagated by conidia, which are observed in large numbers in infected wounds and cystic discharges. The source of infection is the mycelia and conidia of the pathogen wintering under the cover. In persistent varieties, the tissue infected with this disease dries up and falls off within 5-7 days, and the spots are smaller in size. Small purple spots appear on the infected fruits. As the tissue in the spots dies, the fruits crack and the chytre flow starts in that place. The disease infects the plant through shoots in autumn, and in November-December, the surrounding tissue is destroyed by forming necrotic rings. In the fight against the pest, when 10-15% infection is found in the plant (infection in 10-15 out of 100 plants), it is possible to achieve an effective result when using one of the appropriate insecticides.

The red fruit mite (*Metatetranychus ulmi*) feeds by sucking the sap from the cells on the underside of the leaf. A characteristic sign of damage is the formation of light yellow spots along the central vein on the leaves. 79 Later, these spots take on a dull gray color. The red fruit mite develops with 5-7 generations during the vegetation year. According to observations made in 2018-2020, plowing between rows, planting resistant varieties, removing plant residues from the garden, cleaning and bleaching the tree trunk from dead bark play an important role in reducing the population density of the pest. Since ticks infect all organs of the plant, at the end of the growing season, tree trunks should be cleaned with a cod brush, dry branches should be cut, leaves and fruits that have fallen to the ground should be collected and removed from the garden and burned. The rows and between the plants should be kept clean of weeds, they should be mowed frequently and removed from the garden, or herbicides should be used against weeds. In the early spring (when the buds are swollen), it is recommended to use preparations containing mineral oils in chemical control against mites, and during the growing season, when 3-5 mites fall on each leaf surface, one of the appropriate preparations is recommended. The infection rate of curling disease varied between 1-4 points in 2018, 0-4 points in 2019 and 0-3 points in 2020. The average indicator of the degree of infection of peach varieties with leaf curl disease varied from 0.6 to 3 points over the years. Among the varieties, the same relatively low infection (high persistence) in Maliks 25, Netiks 28, Gayoks 30, Rediks 2-110 and Maliks 36 varieties compared to Fedai (n) variety (2 points on average) Netiks 25 (1.7 points), Redix 25 (1.3 points), Netix 30 (1.0 points), Melox 31 (0.6 points), Gayox 35 (1.0 points), Gardeta (0.6 points) varieties were registered. Melox 26 (2.3 points), Redix 27 (2.3 points), Redix 30 (2.3 points), Garteiro (2.3 points), Malix 145 (3 points), Melox 37 (3 points) and Netix 34 (3 points) cultivars showed less resistance to the disease with relatively more infection compared to Fedai (n) cultivar. Compared between varieties, the lowest infection rate was recorded in Melox 31, Gayox 35, Gardeta varieties, and the highest infection rate was recorded in Malix 145, Melox 37 and Netix 34 varieties. Against pests Fedai (n) was selected as a resistant variety with least infestation compared to variety.

References

1. Хамурзаев, С.М. Биологическая и хозяйственная ценность нектарина / С.М.Хамурзаев, Л.С.Гишкаева, И.М. Анасов [и др.]. // Вестник Чеченского государственного университета, -Грозный: -2017. № 3 (27), -с. 47-50.
2. Chen, Ch., William R.O. Characterization of Polymorphic Chloroplast Microsatellites in Prunus Species and Maternal Lineages in Peach Genotypes // Journal of the American Society for Horticultural Science, - 2017. 142(3), - p.217- 224.
3. Anakhanyam Yusifova, Basti Asadova, & Sanubar Aslanova. (2024). SPECIES COMPOSITION AND RESOURCES OF CULTIVATED AND WILD FORAGE PLANTS IN AZERBAIJAN. Deutsche Internationale Zeitschrift Für Zeitgenössische Wissenschaft, 84, 11–14. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12752493>
4. Yusifova A., Asadova B., & Aslanova S. (2024). PLANTS, HUMAN HEALTH AND CIVILIZATION. Norwegian Journal of Development of the International Science, 136. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12745970>
5. Асадова, Б. Г. (2020). Роль фермента глюкозы-6-фосфатдегидрогеназы в адаптации растений к соленым условиям. Spirit Time, (1-1), 6-9.
6. Дуньямалиев, С. А., Мустафаев, З. Х., Асланова, Ф. С., & Гатамов, Х. Р. (2021). Агробиологическая характеристика различных сортов кукурузы и их роль в селекции на влажных почвах Азербайджана. Бюллетень науки и практики, 7(6), 72-79.
7. Girona, E.L. Genetic architecture of agronomic traits in peach [*Prunus persica* (L.)]: subacid, flat shape and nectarine // PhD Thesis, - Barcelona: - Nov., -2014. - p.296.
8. Liu, J., Lindstrom, O.M., Chavez, D.J. Differential Thermal Analysis of 'Elberta' and 'Flavorich' Peach Flower Buds to Predict Cold Hardiness in Georgia // HortScience, - 2019. 54(4), - p.676-683.
9. Salehi, M., Hosseini, S. A. E., Salehi, E., Quaglino, F., & Bianco, P. A. (2020). Peach witches' broom, an emerging disease associated with 'Candidatus Phytoplasma phoenicium' and 'Candidatus Phytoplasma aurantifolia' in Iran. Crop protection, 127, 104946.
10. Aslanova, S. (2023). New Locations of Some Plant Species in the Mountain Part of Yardimli, Lerik and Astara Districts (Azerbaijan). Bulletin of Science and Practice.
11. Decroocq, S., Cornille, A., Tricon, D., Babayeva, S., Chague, A., Eyquard, J. P., ... & Decroocq, V. (2016). New insights into the history of domesticated and wild apricots and its contribution to Plum pox virus resistance. Molecular ecology, 25(19), 4712-4729.
12. Aslanova, S. (2023). Phytocoenological Characteristics and Importance of Vegetation on the Territory of Lerik District (Azerbaijan).
13. Huseynova, N., & Asadova, B. (2024). Study of the Genome Diversity of Cornus L. and Mespilus L. Cultivated in the Northern Regions of Azerbaijan.
14. Zhebentyayeva, T., Ledbetter, C., Burgos, L., & Llácer, G. (2012). Apricot. Fruit breeding, 415-458.
15. Dunyamaliev, S., Mustafaev, Z., Aslanova, F., & Gatamov, K. (2021). Agrobiological Characteristics of Different Varieties of Corn and Their Role in Breeding on Wet Soils in Azerbaijan. Bulletin of Science and Practice.
16. Kurbanov, E., Aslanova, S., & Aslanova, F. (2024). PROTECTION OF THE GENE POOL OF PLANT RESOURCES OF ATROPATENA. (within the Republic of Azerbaijan). Annali D'Italia, 58, 3–7. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13377115>
17. Gharaghani, A., Solhjoo, S., & Oraguzie, N. (2017). A review of genetic resources of almonds and stone fruits (*Prunus* spp.) in Iran.
18. Salimov, V. S., Huseynova, A. S., Abdulaliyeva, S. Ş., Alekberova, M. M., & Aslanova, F. A. (2024). AGROBIOLOGICAL PARAMETERS OF SOME LOCAL, AND INTRODUCED COLLECTIBLE GRAPE VARIETIES, GROWN IN THE CONDITIONS OF THE ABSHERON DISTRICT. Chelonian Research Foundation, 19(01), 283-293.
19. Roy, A. S., & Smith, I. M. (1994). Plum pox situation in Europe. EPPO Bulletin, 24(3), 515-523.
20. Babaev, M. P., Gurbanov, E. A., & Ramazanova, F. M. (2015). Main types of soil degradation in the Kura-Aras Lowland of Azerbaijan. Eurasian soil science, 48, 445-456.
21. Hassanpanah, D., Gurbanov, E., Gadimov, A., & Shahriari, R. (2008). Determination of yield stability in advanced potato cultivars as affected by water deficit and potassium humate in Ardabil region, Iran. Pakistan journal of biological sciences: PJBS, 11(10), 1354-1359.
22. Gurbanov, E. M. (2009). Systematics of higher plants. Baku: BGU, 429.
23. Асланова С. Асадова Б. Флора и фауна Азербайджана. Баку. АДПУ-2023. 345 стр. (In Azerbaijan)
24. Gurbanov E. M. Medicinal plants //Baku: Elm. – 2009.
25. Qurbanov E. M., Cabbarov M. T. Geobotany //Baku: Baku State University publishing house. – 2017.